

Residual energy use and energy efficiency improvement of European supermarket facilities during the post-COVID and energy crisis period

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Abstract

Supermarkets are large consumers of electricity, contributing to the generation of associated polluting emissions. The energy required for its facilities has increased significantly in price in recent years. In Spain, this increase is 10% higher than the average registered in the countries of the European Union (EU). Energy costs have generated an increase in the prices of products sold in supermarkets. Therefore, it is essential to reduce energy consumption, initiating with installations that require the most electricity, such as refrigeration, and take advantage of the residual thermal energy generated in supermarkets. This paper explains the influence of the increase in the cost of energy both in the post-Covid era and the energy crisis and also the evaluation of the energy and environmental achievements with the application of energy improvements and use of residual energy in real supermarkets. The analysis takes into account the current economic-social particularities of the different countries of the EU-27 that modify the economic viability of all the measures. This would achieve an annual energy savings on the order of 70% or 305 kWh/m², as a result avoiding the emission of 122 tons of CO₂ in each supermarket annually, with a recovery period of the necessary investment of 4 years.

Highlights

Improvement of energy efficiency to mitigate the energy cost in supermarkets.

Post-Covid and energy crisis modify energy expenditure in European supermarkets.

Residual thermal energy from refrigeration to reduce HVAC energy consumption.

Waste heat from bakery ovens used to heat water and reduce energy consumption.

Keywords

Supermarkets; Energy saving; Greenhouse gas emissions reduction; Waste heat recovery; Post-Covid; Energy crisis.

Word Count

7776

List of abbreviations

CNMC: Spanish National Markets and Competition Commission

COP: Coefficient of performance

CO₂: Carbon dioxide

CO_{2eq}: Carbon dioxide equivalent

CPI: Consumer price index

DHW: Domestic hot water

EU: European Union

EU-27: European Union-27

HVAC: Heating, ventilation and air conditioning

IDAE: Instituto para la diversificación y ahorro de la energía

IWERS: Integrated waste energy recovery system

LNG: Liquefied natural gas

MWh: Megawatt hour

m²: Square meter

t: Ton

TWh: Terawatt Hour

€: Euro

°C: Degree centigrade

1. Introduction

The health crisis as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic generated a slowdown in economic activity worldwide, directly affecting European countries throughout the year 2020 [1]. When the energy demand was recovering from this blockage, the energy crisis came due to the shortage of natural gas in 2021 [2], aggravated by the cuts in the supply of nuclear energy and weather conditions that led to a reduction in the wind in Europe, reducing electricity generation with eolic energy. The situation was further complicated by the armed conflict between Russia and Ukraine, which generated a series of economic sanctions from the countries of the European Union (EU) towards Russia [3], [4], [5]. This caused the scarcity in the supply of Russian gas to Europe for its combined cycle plants, aggravating the situation of the increase in the cost of energy during the year 2022. In addition, the need to burn lignite coal and hydrocarbons due to the scarce generation of wind and solar energy, increased the costs generated by permits in Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) emissions [6]. In this way, coal futures subject to the EU climate agenda doubled their price and further increased the cost of electricity. Never before have such high prices been paid for electricity within the EU. During the first half of October 2021, the average price of electricity rose to 202.77 euros (€) per megawatt hour (MWh), breaking a new record. This price was 30% higher than the previous month, 156 €/MWh in September 2021 [7]. One can speak of an energy crisis that generated an increase in the cost of products sold in supermarkets and reduced the profits of commercial companies. In the short term, a drop in energy prices is not expected, but rather that they continue to increase throughout 2023 according to data from the World Bank [8]. As a consequence, Spanish supermarkets paid for electricity during the first quarter of 2022 at a rate of 240 €/MWh, a price that is 20% above the EU-27⁽¹⁾ average [9]. Four years ago, the average price paid by these establishments in Spain was more than nine points below the EU 27 average. Thus, the average price during 2018 was 158 €/MWh, while the average price paid in France was 155 €/MWh, in Germany 224 €/MWh, in Italy 198 €/MWh and the average in the EU27 was 172 €/MWh [7]. Going back 10 years, the situation was even more disparate, in 2008 the price that Spain paid for the electricity bill in its supermarkets was just 130 €/MWh, while the EU average

was 160 €/MWh [10]. From the first quarter of 2008 to the first quarter of 2022 the price of electricity in Spanish supermarkets has increased by 66% compared to an increase of 36% in the EU-27 and 39% in the Eurozone⁽²⁾ [7]. The reduction in commercial profits, motivated by the increase in electricity supply costs, has generated an increase in the cost of marketed products, leading to a direct and significant negative impact on the purchasing power of the European population. In Spain, the annual change in the flash estimate of the Consumer Price Index (CPI)⁽³⁾ stood at 9.8% in March 2022, more than two points above the registered in February. The annual rate of the leading indicator of Core Inflation⁽⁴⁾ rose four tenths of a percentage point to 3.4% during 2022 [11]. Additionally, in order to meet the ambitious goals of reducing polluting emissions into the atmosphere, it is essential to minimize energy consumption in non-domestic buildings [12], [13] such as supermarkets.

The originality of this paper lies in calculating for the first time, the savings in energy consumption during the post-COVID and energy crisis period in the most common supermarket model in the EU. This is a period of great uncertainty in energy consumption and with constant increases in its price. Most of the Research done up until now, did not jointly analyze the improvements and uses of energy exposed in this research and do not focus on such a specific and important period in the history. Secondly, all economic data is real and covers all EU-27 countries. Thirdly, the analysis is also novel because it is applied both to efficiency improvements in all energy-consuming installations and to the use of residual energy with its own quantified methods in a real supermarket. More than ever, it is necessary to reduce energy consumption with improvements and innovative methods of harnessing waste energy. Although these aspects seem to be reflected in other sectors such as the industrial, it is not common in the retail sector. Hence this paper is of special relevance and provides real data and methods to be applied both in new facilities and in supermarket reforms. Fourthly, Spain and Portugal (The Iberian Peninsula) are considered an energy island within Europe and also for the first time, data is provided on the increase in the price of energy in the 27 countries of the EU and the particular case of Spain is analyzed in relation to average prices of energy in the EU-27. Fifthly, the results have been

expressed in a double technical and economic way, reflecting the savings in energy and associated polluting emissions but also the recovery periods of the economic investments made in the improvements.

⁽¹⁾ The EU-27 is made up of Germany, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Denmark, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, The Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, the Czech Republic, Romania, Sweden and Cyprus.

⁽²⁾ The Eurozone is made up of Germany, Austria, Belgium, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Estonia, Finland, France, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, the Netherlands, Portugal and Cyprus.

⁽³⁾ The Consumer Price Index (CPI) is a statistical measure of the evolution of the prices of goods and services consumed by the population that resides in family dwellings in Spain.

⁽⁴⁾ The Core Inflation is the inflation reflected by the consumer price index when it does not take into account neither energy products nor unprocessed food products.

1.1. Reasons for the rise in the price of energy

1.1.1. The COVID-19 pandemic

The COVID pandemic that Spanish and European society experienced during the 2020-2021 period generated a brake on economic activity, therefore, on electricity consumption [14]. However, during the first half of 2020, the lockdown generated by the state of alarm decreed in most countries took place and the population stockpiled products from supermarkets, considerably increasing their energy consumption. On the other hand, the forced confinements of part of European society and the reduction of activities such as leisure led to lower energy demand. This reduction in consumption forced fuel and energy producers to slow down their

production until the pandemic lockdowns were lifted. In 2021, with the lifting of part of the lockdowns and the return to normal commercial activity, the market recovered so quickly that the production of energy and fuels could not adequately meet the demand [15], [16], [17], [18]. In addition, weather conditions in Europe and the rise of teleworking led to an increase in heating consumption during 2021 [19], [20], [21]. Furthermore, during that same year, the influence of geopolitical factors led to a decrease in gas supply due to part of non-EU countries. Thus, Spain saw its availability of gas reduced when the supply from Algeria through the gas pipeline that crossed Morocco was cut off. Although the supply was replaced with the chartering of liquefied natural gas (LNG) carriers, which also made it possible to buy in a global market but at a higher cost as transport prices had increased. The latter generated a shortage of energy fuels such as gas, which caused the prices of these products to increase throughout the world and especially in Europe.

1.1.2. EU environmental policies

European environmental policies aimed at decarbonizing the energy sector have been increased in recent years. In 2020, the EU signed the Paris agreements that oblige it to reduce its polluting emissions by a minimum of 55% by 2030 with respect to 1990 levels. Additionally, the EU signed the Katowice climate package to promote the implementation of the Agreement of Paris [22], [23]. Therefore, the EU and particularly Spain, drastically reduced from 2020 the production of energy with polluting sources that emit CO₂, increasing the price of CO₂ emission rights [24]. Thus, in Spain in January 2020 the price of these rights was 24.75 € and in December 2021 it was 80 € [25]. In addition, in Spain this change in the energy paradigm accelerated during 2020 with the closure of most of the thermal power plants that generated electricity by using coal. This led to a reduction in the self-sufficiency of energy with its own sources. Other EU countries also undertook important changes in energy generation models throughout 2020, eliminating energy generation with sources such as hydrocarbons and coal creating a situation of economic exposure

to foreign fuel prices, especially the price of natural gas marketed by Russia, Syria and other non-European countries.

1.1.3. The natural gas price

According to Eurostat, the demand for natural gas represents 20% of electricity production in Europe [26]. In addition, given the design of the European electricity market, the natural gas price largely determines the price of electricity [27]. In March 2022, this price had multiplied by five in one year, rising 25% since the beginning of the Russian invasion of Ukraine [7]. The reasons for the increase in gas prices, which were at very low levels before and during the pandemic, had to do with having coincided with the famous bottlenecks and other temporary factors, such as the reduction in production and investments due to the halt in demand in March 2020, followed by a very cold winter and spring 2021. This reduced the reserves stored in Europe. Additionally, China shifted part of its consumption from coal to gas, Russia curbed gas sales to Europe, and the United States stopped extracting shale gas during the pandemic. The EU depends on imported gas, suffering the increase in price. Russia has historically been the largest supplier of natural gas to the EU [28]. After the Russia-Ukraine-Europe gas disputes of 2006 and 2009, followed by tensions in the wake of the Ukraine crisis of 2013-2014, the EU sought to reduce its dependence on Russian natural gas imports [29]. However, at the beginning of 2022 Russia was still supplying around 40% of the EU's gas consumption [30], [31]. The price of fuels used in power generation was greatly increased by factors such as the reduction of Russian oil and gas due to the sanctions applied by the EU to Russia for the war against Ukraine, this resulted in a decrease in fuel available worldwide, increasing its prices [3], [4]. Thus, the main factors that affected the price of electricity not only in Spain, but also in the rest of the EU countries were:

- The electricity production mix available at any given time.
- The price of CO₂ emission rights.
- The price of fossil fuels.

- Weather conditions.
- The demand for energy by the consumer.
- The military conflict between Russia and Ukraine.

Without the combination of all these factors, the effect of this increase in the price of electricity in Spain and the rest of the EU due to the increase in the cost of gas should not have been so important in the final rate for consumers. Since, particularly in Spain, the weight of gas in the electricity generation mix is low, with nuclear, renewable and hydraulic production contributing around 70%. The reason why the rise in electricity prices has caused such a stir was that in 2022 around 35% of Spanish consumers, although only 12% demand, had regulated rates. Due to a political decision of the EU, these rates were linked to the pool price, and this is formed through a marginal system (the price of the most expensive unit sets the price of the system). In other European countries, this relationship between gas and consumer rates is not so close.

1.2. The great consumption of electrical energy in supermarkets

According to the report by the consulting firm Savills, the total stock of food surfaces in Spain reached 16.7 million square meters and 24,522 establishments in 2022. The figure includes hypermarkets, supermarkets, discount stores, cash & carry, convenience stores and specialty stores. This allocation represents an increase of 1% in the sales room and 8% in the number of establishments compared to 2019. In 2021, the food sector was the main driver of retail investment in Spain [32]. The supermarket formats according to their size and their percentage in Spain in 2020 are reflected in Table 1 [33], [34], [35]. These values can be assimilated to the rest of Europe.

Table 1. Formats of supermarkets according to their surface

Type of supermarket	Exhibition and sales area (m ²)	Comercial area in 2020 (%)
Small supermarket	100-399	12
Medium supermarket	400-999	36
Large supermarket	1000-2499	32
Hypermarket	> 2500	20

Consumer habits are in the midst of transformation and distributors, aware of this, are accelerating the integration of technology in all their processes. The food retail sector in Spain has experienced a revolution in the online channel in the last five years. Its volume increased by almost 600 million euros, increasing during the first quarter of 2021 by 106% [32]. Delivery has also increased its presence, incorporating new technologies and increasing the areas of refrigeration and processed products. This trend is common throughout Europe. In addition, food retail, and especially supermarkets, have the highest energy consumption in relation to the commercial area. This is mainly due to the need for refrigeration of a large number of the products they offer. Although the energy consumed in a modern supermarket is simultaneously distributed in refrigeration for food storage, lighting, heating or cooling to maintain the conditions of the internal space [36]. Electricity consumption values were obtained based on the useful area of the establishment between 440-600 kWh/m²·year, depending on the weather conditions in which the establishment is located [37]. Consequently, modern supermarket chains are responsible for 3% to 5% of total global electricity consumption [38].

In 2011, the percentages of electricity consumption in a typical supermarket in the United Kingdom depending, among other factors, on the format of the establishment and the commercial practices or the mix of products for sale were established [39]. The results, corresponding to a supermarket model similar to the one analyzed, were 15%-25% for lighting, 30%-60% for industrial refrigeration and 25% for air conditioning, ventilation and bakery. In 2018, Ríos &

Roqueñí obtained the following percentages of electricity consumption for a Spanish supermarket with similar characteristics: 29.68% lighting, 49.55% refrigeration, 8.14% Heating, Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC), 9.55% bakery, 0.41% hot water, 1.61% plugs and 1.06% others [40]. As can be seen, the data from both investigations with small variations as a result of the different climatology that affects the consumption of the facilities and the consideration of the consumption by the bakery ovens in the Spanish case are directly related.

2. Material and methods

The methodology used consisted of the analysis of the energy consumption of a real supermarket located in Spain, studying the different areas and existing facilities in the supermarket. The chosen supermarket corresponds to the most common establishment model in terms of surface area, age and sales areas. With a commercial area between 1000 and 1500 m² and sections for butchers, delicatessens, fishmongers, greengrocers and bakeries, as well as a public patio with self-service product sales. The supermarket was 15 years old, with facilities that had not been renovated since its inauguration. The age also corresponds to that of most commercial establishments of this type existing in Spain and Europe [32]. The measurement of the energy consumption of all the areas that could be improved was carried out between 2016 and 2017 during twelve months (1 year). The energy consumption in 2018-2021 was also obtained after the adoption of the energy saving measures that were applied in the reform carried out in 2017. To carry this out, individual energy analyzers were placed in the secondary lighting, industrial cooling, air conditioning, ventilation and the bakery section with its pastry and bakery manufacturing ovens. Subsequently, the supermarket was completely refurbished, replacing all its facilities.

The supermarket lighting reform consisted of the following actions:

- People detection systems for ignition. The use of these systems prevents the lighting from remaining on when there is no occupation of people in the area and therefore it is not necessary.

- Photoelectric cells. As with the previous systems, it is intended not to use artificial lighting at times when it is not necessary. With the use of photoelectric cells in the lighting closest to windows or areas with natural lighting, the use of lighting in areas and moments in which natural lighting is sufficient is avoided.
- Lighting controllers for advertising signs. In addition to the use of ignition programmers, the use of light detectors is useful to avoid unnecessary lighting of the signs. These are especially useful in spring and summer.
- Led lighting. Replacement of all fluorescent and incandescent lighting with LED technology. The installation was carried out maintaining the criteria of light intensity and using LED luminaires of proven quality.

The reform in the air conditioning and ventilation facilities of the supermarket consisted of the following actions:

- Air conditioning temperature control. The correct regulation of temperature, humidity and outside air intake allows significant savings in energy consumption to be achieved. The variation of one degree Celsius in the programmed comfort temperature in HVAC equipment generates an increase in electricity consumption between 5-8% [41].
- Use of Inverter technology. The use of HVAC equipped with Inverter technology avoided the starts and stops of traditional equipment, reducing the energy consumption of compressors. These equipments allow their operation to be regulated continuously depending on the temperature programmed for the supermarket. By using these equipments a greater sensation of comfort was also experienced as the temperature was maintained in a more stable way. The savings that can be achieved with this equipment exceed 30% [42]. In addition, they maintained their performance more steadily even at lower air intake temperatures. The inconvenience they presented was that the Inverter technology increases the price of the equipment.
- Free-cooling. With the use of this technology, part of the energy consumption used in the refrigeration of the supermarket was avoided by taking advantage of the outside air for

this purpose. The air intake was electronically controlled through the use of temperature sensors both outside and inside the premises. It was also necessary to filter the inlet air to eliminate possible impurities.

The supermarket refrigeration reform consisted of the following measures:

- Refrigerated cabinets with glass doors. The substitution of open cabinets for closed cabinets with glass doors reduced the necessary cooling capacity and hence the consumption of electrical energy required by the refrigeration plants. This measure also kept the temperature of the supermarket more stable in winter, avoiding the cold areas with open furniture which increase the energy consumption of the air conditioning system.
- Use of high-efficiency refrigeration plants and refrigerants with low global warming potential. The replacement of the traditional multi-circuit plants, which are rather inefficient, with refrigeration plants considerably reduced energy consumption. The installation was divided into two refrigeration systems, one for positive cold and one for negative cold. The refrigeration plants were also equipped with additional measures such as frequency variators in compressors and condensers, electronic regulation of defrosts and electronic expansion and floating condensation valves which increased their efficiency. In addition, environmentally friendly refrigerants were also used.

The residual heat that the condensers of the industrial cooling installation evacuated to the outside of the engine room was used. The most important uses of the heat generated during the thermodynamic processes that take place in the refrigeration installation are the following:

- Defrosting in cabinets and freezers through the use of hot gas from the discharge of the compressors. In this way, the electrical resistors necessary to eliminate the ice that was deposited on the evaporators due to the condensation of ambient humidity were dispensed with. Energy expenditure was reduced, preventing the resistors from periodically

consuming energy to transform it into heat and carry out the essential defrost process so that the evaporators do not malfunction.

- In the industrial cold generation processes, residual hot air was obtained, which instead of being discharged in its entirety outside the supermarket, was partially recovered to improve the performance of the air conditioning equipment and, consequently, reduce the energy consumption. The design reflected in Figure 1 where motorized dampers in the hot air discharge ducts of the condensing units of the refrigeration system were placed. One damper in each of the hot air outlets of the two refrigeration plants towards the discharge chimney to the outside and another damper in the duct that communicates with the air conditioning machine room were also placed. These gates were equipped with opening regulation depending on the temperature of the air conditioning engine room. Hence, when the temperature of the air conditioning engine room dropped below 10 °C, the hot air from the refrigeration process was discharged into the air conditioning engine room until the temperature of 10 °C was recovered in this room. When the temperature of the air conditioning machine room reached 10 °C the damper in the duct that connects that room to the cold extraction was closed and the dampers that allowed the hot air coming from the cooling plants to be evacuated through the chimney were opened. With this improvement, it was possible, on the one hand, not to penalize cold condensation and on the other hand to improve the air intake conditions of the air conditioning equipment in winter. In this way, increases in the air intake temperature in winter of the order of 10 °C were achieved. This made it possible to increase the COP of the air conditioning installation and, thus, reduce the electrical consumption of the heat pumps.

Fig. 1. Location of the elements for taking advantage of the residual heat from refrigeration in the air conditioning and industrial cooling machine rooms

The reform in the bakery facilities of the supermarket included the incorporation of the integrated waste energy recovery system (IWERS) in the electric bread ovens. Through this system, which is described in [43], the residual heat from the condensation of bread ovens is used. The system recovers the heat generated during the manufacturing processes of the bakery products in the ovens. This thermal energy is used to heat Domestic Hot Water (DHW) in the supermarket. Figure 2 plots a scheme of the main system. In our analysis, this system was used in the two ovens in a supermarket similar to the analyzed one. The IWERS not only reduces the consumption of electrical energy used to obtain DHW, but also achieves a significant reduction in the consumption of clean water used in the condensation of the steam generated in the ovens.

Fig. 2. IWERS circuit diagram

This also made it possible to obtain consumption data from the different areas of commerce once the improvements in energy efficiency and use of residual energy were applied. The results are especially interesting because they reflect the changes in commercial behavior, consumption, energy prices in the post-Covid situation and the energy crisis experienced in Europe. The values obtained were compared with similar analyzes carried out by other authors in European supermarkets in the pre-Covid era. A comparative analysis of the costs of electrical energy consumed in supermarkets during the last 10 years, both in Spain and in the rest of the EU27 countries, was also carried out. This allowed to have a broader view of the savings in energy and associated polluting emissions that were achieved with the implementation of the improvements presented. Additionally, the investment in improvements was evaluated and the amortization was calculated. Math formula to calculate the amortization period of the investment was common in all types of improvements, being:

$$A = \frac{C}{S} \quad (1)$$

where A (year) is the amortization, C (€) is the cost of applying energy improvements and S (€/year) is the financial savings achieved with the application of energy improvements.

3. Results

Table 2 details the electricity prices for non-household consumers, according to [7] for European countries, the average price for the 27 countries of the EU and for the 19 countries of the euro area. The half-yearly average prices (S) are detailed from 2018 to the end of 2021, applicable to the electricity consumed in European supermarkets. The years 2018 and 2019 constitute the pre-Covid period. The year 2020 was the year of lockdowns in Europe and therefore the most important Covid period. During the year 2021 the Covid de-escalation begins, the European population was no longer subject to confinements in general and was considered as the beginning of the Post-Covid Period, above all the second semester.

Table 2. Electricity prices for non-household consumers, for European countries. Average price for the 27 countries of the EU and for the 19 countries of the euro area

	S1	S2	S1	S2	S1	S2	S1	S2
	2018	2018	2019	2019	2020	2020	2021	2021
Denmark	0.2807	0.2787	0.2628	0.2604	0.2524	0.2622	0.2900	0.3291
Germany	0.2231	0.2256	0.2298	0.2232	0.2404	0.2378	0.3193	0.2556
Italy	0.1968	0.1999	0.2237	0.2213	0.2057	0.1992	0.2259	0.2485
Portugal	0.1835	0.1839	0.1703	0.1807	0.1745	0.1716	0.2089	0.1844
Cyprus	0.1794	0.2201	0.2075	0.2192	0.1928	0.1661	0.1976	0.2303
Ireland	0.1772	0.1823	0.1843	0.1826	0.1886	0.1860	0.2555	0.2375
Netherlands	0.1737	0.1277	0.1654	0.1291	0.1796	0.1399	0.1281	0.1620
Belgium	0.1727	0.1841	0.1923	0.1848	0.1872	0.1821	0.2702	0.2159
Greece	0.1632	0.1627	0.1569	0.1534	0.1492	0.1536	0.1680	0.2556
Slovakia	0.1617	0.1650	0.1768	0.1812	0.1849	0.1856	0.1668	0.1900
Malta	0.1596	0.1600	0.1593	0.1596	0.1593	0.1595	0.1279	0.1594
Latvia	0.1570	0.1560	0.1567	0.1583	0.1539	0.1563	0.1403	0.1880
France	0.1514	0.1440	0.1568	0.1519	0.1702	0.1515	0.1403	0.1542
Czechia	0.1507	0.1565	0.1661	0.1716	0.1735	0.1680	0.1802	0.1674
Austria	0.1463	0.1480	0.1522	0.1514	0.1614	0.1624	0.2216	0.1796
Spain	0.1445	0.1718	0.1791	0.1741	0.1767	0.1790	0.2323	0.1774
Poland	0.1404	0.1403	0.1502	0.1335	0.1616	0.1599	0.1548	0.1697
Croatia	0.1293	0.1294	0.1387	0.1430	0.1385	0.1352	0.1291	0.1530
Slovenia	0.1289	0.1292	0.1380	0.1812	0.1402	0.1419	0.1662	0.1440
Hungary	0.1253	0.1240	0.1415	0.1400	0.1443	0.1396	0.1003	0.1489
Montenegro	0.1150	0.1131	0.1223	0.1235	0.1259	0.0978	0.0980	0.0974
Estonia	0.1148	0.1243	0.1198	0.1180	0.1063	0.1135	0.1324	0.1974

Lithuania	0.1134	0.1246	0.1252	0.1275	0.1298	0.1386	0.1348	0.1908
Bulgaria	0.1130	0.1162	0.1194	0.1136	0.1117	0.1150	0.1024	0.1853
Romania	0.1119	0.1161	0.1275	0.1136	0.1422	0.1389	0.1536	0.1643
Luxembourg	0.1118	0.1147	0.1199	0.1201	0.1269	0.1267	0.1988	0.1323
Moldova	0.1089	0.1038	0.1005	0.1036	0.1269	0.1267	0.0851	0.0810
Finland	0.1033	0.1077	0.1092	0.1093	0.1068	0.1130	0.1767	0.1160
Bosnia and								
Herzegovina	0.1016	0.0981	0.1029	0.1027	0.1061	0.1061	0.0875	0.1041
Kosovo	0.1013	0.1018	0.0874	0.0881	0.0878	0.1061	0.0605	0.0889
Serbia	0.1002	0.1032	0.1124	0.1142	0.1135	0.1109	0.0791	0.1227
North Macedonia	0.0997	0.1025	0.1051	0.1073	0.1087	0.1071	0.0841	0.1935
Sweden	0.0993	0.1068	0.1131	0.1035	0.1090	0.1032	0.1791	0.1497
Norway	0.0986	0.1117	0.1051	0.0969	0.0640	0.0610	0.1826	0.1489
Iceland	0.0919	0.0878	0.0888	0.0893	0.0640	0.0816	0.1356	0
Ukraine	0.0752	0.0779	0.0822	0.0893	0.0759	0.0686	0.0485	0
Turkey	0.0727	0.0754	0.0891	0.1023	0.0997	0.0829	0.0834	0.087
Georgia	0.0645	0.0743	0.0781	0.0625	0.0660	0.0579	0.0631	0.0808
Albania	0	0	0.1248	0	0	0	0	0
Liechtenstein	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.2071	0
Euro area								
(19 countries)	0.1809	0.1818	0.1927	0.1865	0.1961	0.1882	0.2322	0.2074
European Union								
(27 countries)	0.1715	0.1727	0.1830	0.1766	0.1865	0.1797	0.2192	0.2001

3.1. Distribution of electricity consumption in the analyzed and unreformed supermarket in the post-Covid period

Table 3 shows the results obtained in the unreformed supermarket analyzed in the pre-Covid stage. The results of both investigations mentioned in section 1.2 were consistent with the percentages reflected in Table 3. The small variations with increases in Refrigeration or Industrial Cooling may be due to the growing trend of commercialization of refrigerated products, as well as the slight increase in the production of bakery products.

Table 3. Distribution of annual electrical consumption per m² of usable surface area of unreformed supermarket and percentages

	Annual consumption/useful area	Percentage
	(kWh/m²·year)	(%)
Lighting	129.47	27.98
Refrigeration	229.83	49.68
HVAC	45.12	9.75
Bakery	44.11	9.53
Hot Water	1.68	0.36
Plugs	7.89	1.72
Others	4.55	0.98

Next, the results obtained with the energy improvements applied in the reforms of the different supermarket facilities will be reflected. The electricity consumption data was collected during six-monthly periods of four years in order to collect seasonal and social variations in the consumption needs of the different lighting and thermal installations, as well as in the production and sale of products.

3.2. Reform of the lighting installation

Table 4 shows the economic concepts of annual energy consumption savings, economic savings and savings in associated polluting emissions, which are achieved with the improvements made to the lighting installation. The results were obtained for the two semesters of 2018, 2019, 2020 and 2021 according to the energy prices provided by Eurostat [7]. In Spain, the carbon footprint for energy consumption or Carbon Dioxide Equivalent was 0.321 kg CO₂/kWh in 2018, 0.241 kg CO₂/kWh in 2019, 0.250 kg CO₂/kWh in 2020 and 0.259 kg CO_{2eq}/kWh in 2021 depending on the mix of the Spanish electricity network published by the Spanish National Markets and Competition Commission (CNMC) [44]. In the EU27 the average footprint in 2021 was 0.2307 kg CO_{2eq}/kWh according to data from the European Environment Agency dependent on the EU [45].

Table 4. Savings achieved with the reform of the lighting installation

	Savings in electricity consumption	Savings in Spain	Savings in EU27	Savings in CO₂ production from Spain
	(kWh/semester)	(€/semester)	(€/semester)	(kg CO₂/semester)
1st Semester 2018	63,041.66	9,109.52	10,811.64	20,236.37
2nd Semester 2018	63,672.08	10,938.86	10,996.11	20,438.74
1st Semester 2019	61,780.83	11,064.95	11,305.89	14,889.18
2nd Semester 2019	64,308.80	11,196.16	11,356.93	15,498.42
1st Semester 2020	68,715.41	12,142.01	12,815.42	17,178.85
2nd Semester 2020	66,855.68	11,967.17	12,013.97	16,713.92
1st Semester 2021	64,932.91	15,083.91	14,233.29	16,817.62
2nd Semester 2021	64,945.52	11,521.33	12,995.60	16,820.89

3.3. Reform of the air conditioning and ventilation facilities

Table 5 shows the economic concepts of annual energy consumption savings, economic savings and savings in associated polluting emissions, which are achieved with the improvements made in the air conditioning and ventilation installation.

Table 5. Savings achieved with the reform of the HVAC installation

	Savings in electricity consumption (kWh/semester)	Savings in Spain (€/semester)	Savings in EU27 (€/semester)	Savings in CO₂ production from Spain (kg CO₂/semester)
1st Semester 2018	12,658.83	1829.20	2170.99	4063.48
2nd Semester 2018	12,785.41	2196.53	2208.04	4104.12
1st Semester 2019	12,405.65	2221.85	2270.23	2989.76
2nd Semester 2019	12,913.27	2248.20	2280.48	3112.10
1st Semester 2020	13,798.12	2438.13	2573.35	3449.53
2nd Semester 2020	13,424.68	2403.02	2412.42	3356.17
1st Semester 2021	13,038.59	3028.86	2858.06	3376.99
2nd Semester 2021	13,041.12	2313.49	2609.53	3377.65

3.4. Reform of the refrigeration installation

Table 6 shows the economic concepts of annual energy consumption savings, economic savings and savings in associated polluting emissions, which are achieved with the improvements made in the refrigeration facility.

Table 6. Savings achieved with the reform of the refrigeration installation

	Savings in electricity consumption (kWh/semester)	Savings in Spain (€/semester)	Savings in EU27 (€/semester)	Savings in CO₂ production from Spain (kg CO₂/semester)
1st Semester 2018	143,748.90	20,771.72	24,652.94	46,143.40
2nd Semester 2018	145,186.39	24,943.02	25,073.69	46,604.83
1st Semester 2019	140,873.92	25,230.52	25,779.93	33,950.62
2nd Semester 2019	146,638.25	25,529.72	25,896.32	35,339.82
1st Semester 2020	156,686.30	27,686.47	29,222.00	39,171.58
2nd Semester 2020	152,445.71	27,287.78	27,394.49	38,111.43
1st Semester 2021	148,061.37	34,394.66	32,455.05	38,347.89
2nd Semester 2021	148,090.12	26,271.19	29,632.83	38,355.34

3.5. Use of thermal energy or residual heat

The use of residual thermal energy generated by the activity of the supermarket was carried out in the following two areas of commerce.

3.5.1. Residual heat from bakery ovens

The IWERS not only reduced the consumption of electrical energy used to obtain DHW, but also achieved a significant reduction in the consumption of clean water used in the condensation of the steam generated in the ovens.

3.5.2. Energy use of residual hot air from cooling plants

This system turned out to be especially recommendable in the coldest times of the year, achieving savings in energy consumption of over 20%. When the outside temperature was higher and it was not necessary to supply hot air to the room where the cooling plants were located, the motorized gates remained closed, preventing the circulation of hot air from the cooling plants to the air conditioning room. With the use of this system of thermal energy use, it was possible to reduce the electrical energy consumed by the HVAC by more than 10% per year.

Table 7 shows the economic concepts of annual energy consumption savings, economic savings and savings in associated polluting emissions, which are achieved by making use of the residual heat generated in the supermarket.

Table 7. Savings achieved with the use of thermal energy or residual heat

	Savings in electricity consumption (kWh/semester)	Savings in Spain (€/semester)	Savings in EU27 (€/semester)	Savings in CO₂ production from Spain (kg CO ₂ /semester)
1st Semester 2018	2562.50	370.28	439.47	822.56
2nd Semester 2018	2581.15	443.44	445.76	828.55
1st Semester 2019	2506.30	448.88	458.65	604.02
2nd Semester 2019	2597.80	452.28	458.77	626.07
1st Semester 2020	2793.13	493.55	520.92	698.28
2nd Semester 2020	2710.21	485.13	487.02	677.55
1st Semester 2021	2569.35	596.86	563.20	665.46
2nd Semester 2021	2632.77	467.05	526.82	681.89

3.6. Annual savings achieved with the application of energy improvements and amortization periods of the required investments

The savings obtained in the Spanish supermarket can be extrapolated to the whole of the EU27 as they present similar socioeconomic characteristics. Therefore, if in 2022 the population of Spain was 47,435,597 inhabitants and in the EU27 it was 447,135,481 inhabitants [46], [47], with the adoption of the proposed energy saving measures, the detailed savings are estimated in Table 8 for the total number of existing supermarkets.

Table 8. Savings achieved with the reform of Spanish and European supermarkets

	Energy savings (TWh/year)	Economic savings (M€/year)	Annual savings in CO ₂ production (t CO ₂ /year)
Spain	11.214	2297.23	290.45x10 ⁷
UE27	105.707	22,161.41	243.87x10 ⁸

The investment in improvements to the lighting installation amounted to 57,920.50 € (C); at 11,700 € (C) the improvements in the HVAC facility; at 90,850 € (C) the improvements in the refrigeration facility and at 3900 € (C) the improvements in the use of thermal energy or residual heat. Figure 3 shows the average annual financial savings (S) during the 2018-2021 period and the investment amortization periods (A) of the different improvements applied to the supermarket.

Fig. 3. Application of energy saving measures in the supermarket. Average annual financial savings during 2018-2021 period (€/year) and investment amortization periods (years)

4. Conclusion

The main strategy to alleviate the effects of the increase in electricity prices in supermarkets must consist of improving the energy efficiency of the facilities by taking advantage of the residual heat generated.

The measures which generated the maximum savings were those applied to the refrigeration installation analyzed. In addition, they presented the shortest investment recovery period, under 2 years.

The second measures that presented the best results were those applied to the lighting installation. The savings were half of those achieved in refrigeration but were still rather significant. They also presented short amortization periods, not exceeding 2.5 years.

The third most important measures turned out to be those applied to HVAC systems. The payback periods for this investment were one year higher than those for lighting, not exceeding 3.5 years.

The measures that presented the longest recovery periods, 4.5 years, and the lowest savings were the measures applied to bakery ovens. These, with a reduced investment of less than 1 €/m² of useful surface area of the establishment are the most economical measures to apply.

All the proposed measures present rather short periods of amortization of the economic increase that the implementation of the improvements entailed. In no case did they exceed 5 years. Hence, they were economically highly recommended measures.

The price of energy is expected to continue to rise, so these amortization periods will be even shorter.

Considering the measures that achieved the greatest environmental maximization of the investment, improvements in refrigeration take first place, with 65% of the total reduction in emissions. They are followed by improvements in the lighting installation with 28%, in the HVAC with 6% and finally the connections in the bakery with 1% of the total.

All the measures proposed can have a truly significant influence on the achievement of the polluting emission reduction policies assumed by the EU and on the containment or reduction of the prices of the products sold in supermarkets, since the rises in energy costs would have less impact. In the four-year period analysed, the economic improvements achieved in all the EU27 countries could have been calculated. In our case, these improvements turned out to be 3.8% higher in the EU average than in Spain.

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